

D7.4. Report on Status of Posting of Results – Study A

S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], N. Portokallidis [ATHENA], I. Drougka [PHAZE],
E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

Due Date: 31 Mar 2025

Delivery Date: 25 Nov 2025

Horizon Innovation Action | Agreement No. 101137227
HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Co-funded by the European Union

ThrombUS+ Consortium

ATHENA	Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies, Greece	Eleni Kaldoudi kaldoudi@athenarc.gr
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology Lithuania	Vaidotas Marozas vaidotas.marozas@ktu.lt
VERMON	Vermont SA France	Mathieu Legros m.legros@vermon.com
FRAUNHOFER	Institute for Photonic Microsystems, Fraunhofer Germany	Nicolas Lange Nicolas.Lange@ipms.fraunhofer.de
TELEMED	Telemed Ultrasound Medical Systems Lithuania	Dmitry Novikov d.novikov@pcultrasound.com
EchoNous	EchoNous Inc USA	Pavlos Moustakidis pavlos.moustakidis@echonous.com
MEDIS	medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH Germany	Susann Balling sb@medis.company
ComfTech	ComfTech SLR Italy	Lara Alessia Moltani alessia.moltani@comfttech.com
TAU	Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology Tampere University, Finland	Antti Vehkaoja antti.vehkaoja@tuni.fi
LMSU	Lithuanian University of Health Science Lithuania	Andrius Macas andrius.macas@ismu.lt
GNP	Papageorgiou General Hospital Greece	Maria Bigaki pmo@papageorgiou-hospital.gr
CSS-IRCCS	Home Relief of Suffering Hospital Italy	Elvira Grandone e.grandone@operapadrepio.it
HSV	Simon Veil Hospital France	Maxime Gautier maxime.gautier@ch-simoneveil.fr
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies, Germany	Thorsten Prinz thorsten.prinz@vde.com
MEDEA	MEDEA SRL Italy	Pietro Dionisio p.dionisio@medeaproject.eu
PHAZE	Clinical Research and Pharma Consulting SA Greece	Spiros Anagnostopoulos spiros.anagnostopoulos@phazeclinical.com
PBY	PredictBy Research and Consulting SL Spain	Frans Folkvord ffolkvord@predictby.com
SciGen	SciGen Technologies SA Greece	Katerina Pavlidi katerina.Pavlidi@scigentech.com

Disclaimer

This document contains description of the ThrombUS+ project work, findings, and products. The authors of this document have taken any available measure for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority HADEA can be held responsible for them.

In case you believe that this document harms in any way intellectual property held by you as a person or as a representative of an entity, please do notify us immediately.

ThrombUS+ is an Innovation Action Project co-funded by the European Union, under HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05 "Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery".

Document Control Page

Project

Grant Agreement:	101137227
Acronym:	ThrombUS+
Title:	Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis
Type:	Innovation Action
Start:	1 January 2024
End:	30 June 2027
Programme:	Horizon Europe
Call Identifier:	HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Call Topic	Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery
Website:	http://thrombus.eu/

Deliverable

#	24
No:	D7.4
Deliverable Title:	Report on Status of Posting of Clinical Studies - Study A
Deliverable Type:	R
Classification:	PU
Task:	T7.2. Clinical Study A – conventional US data collection
Task Leader:	PHAZE [I. Drougka]
Work Package:	7. Clinical studies [M01-M42]
Work Package Leader:	PHAZE [I. Drougka]
Responsible Partner:	PHAZE
Authors:	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], N. Portokallidis [ATHENA], I. Drougka [PHAZE], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]
Input from:	Clinical partners
Peer Reviewers:	T. Prinz [VDE], A. Fiska [ATHENA]
Due Date:	31 Mar 2025 [M15]
Delivery Date:	25 Nov 2025

Document Status

Version:	1.0
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consortium reviewed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP leader endorsed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator endorsed

Revision History			
Version	Date	Modification	Contributors
0.1	10 Nov 2025	New content, deliverable layout	E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]
0.2	15 Nov 2025	ISF, Version 1.0_26sep2024/ TMF, Version 1.0_26sep2024	I. Drougka [PHAZE]
0.3	20 Nov 2025	Study A data set description	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA] N. Portokallidis [ATHENA]
0.4	25 Nov 2025	Comments from reviewers	T. Prinz [VDE], A. Fiska [ATHENA]
1.0	25 Nov 2025	Editing for conformity	E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

Contents

About ThrombUS+	1
Deliverable D7.4 Description	1
Cite this Document as	1
Terms and Definitions.....	2
Executive Summary	3
1. Study A Registration and Posting of Results	4
2. Study A Progress and Plan for Completion	5
ANNEX: ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1	7
<i>Data collection overview</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Data set #1 overview</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>Overview of the Training and Testing Subsets</i>	<i>10</i>

About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D7.4 Description

WP7 aims to deploy a series of clinical studies, including three cohort studies for data collection, an early feasibility study, and a prospective, double-blinded, pilot study of the ThrombUS+ system.

Study A is a multi-center cohort study that aims to collect and create a labelled ultrasound data set containing ultrasound images series of patients that undergo routine ultrasound scans because of suspected deep vein thrombosis. The data will be used to train the AI model for automated detection of deep vein thrombosis on conventional ultrasound scans and also will be made available through the EOSC for research purposes.

This deliverable provides a report on the posting of the current status of the posting of results of Study A.

Cite this Document as

Didaskalou S, N Portokallidis, Drougka I, Kaldoudi E, Report on Status of Posting of Results – Study A, Deliverable 7.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 25 November 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17641971>

Abbreviations and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
CSV	Comma separated values
CVF	Common femoral vein
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
FV	Femoral vein
GSV	Great saphenous vein
L	Left
ID	Identification
PGNA	University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli, Greece
Pop	Popliteal vein
PV	Popliteal vein
R	Right
SD	Standard deviation
US	Ultrasound

Executive Summary

The ThrombUS+ Study A is registered on ClinicalTrials.gov (ID: NCT06989255).

The resulting data, protocol, and manuals are deposited in Zenodo and shared on Kaggle.

Software for data anonymization developed for the purposes of the study is available as open source via GitHub.

1. Study A Registration and Posting of Results

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A is registered in ClinicalTrials.gov platform, ID: NCT06989255.

Protocol, data collection and annotation manual and resulting data sets are also deposited in Zenodo. The first Study A dataset is publicly available in ThrombUS+ community in Zenodo.

The dataset and its description are also posted on the Kaggle¹ as part of the 1st data challenge organized by the ThrombUS+ consortium.

Ultrasound DICOM data anonymizer software is available via GitHub.

A detailed account of the Study A outcomes and posting status is given in the table below.

ThrombUS+ Study A registration and posting of results			
Study A outcome	Platform	Date	Link
Protocol	ClinicalTrials.gov	25.05.2025	https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06989255?term=ThrombUS%20Study-A&rank=1
Protocol	Zenodo	28.05.2024	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371924
Ultrasound Data Collection Manual	Zenodo	20.08.2025	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16913651
Ultrasound Data Annotation Manual	Zenodo	20.08.2025	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16912105
Ultrasound Data Anonymizer	GitHub	26.05.2025	https://github.com/thrombusplus/US-DICOMizer
Training data set #1	Zenodo	21.11.2025	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17659415
Testing data set #1	Zenodo	21.11.2025	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17664207
Challenge 1.1. on Training and Testing data set #1	Kaggle	25.11.2025	https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/Thrombus_challenge_1_1
Challenge 1.1. on Training and Testing data set #1	Kaggle	25.11.2025	https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/Thrombus_challenge_1_2
Training data set #2	Zenodo	June 2026	pending
Testing data set #2	Zenodo	June 2026	pending
Training data set #3	Zenodo	Feb 2027	pending
Testing data set #3	Zenodo	Feb 2027	pending
Complete data set with ground truth	Zenodo ClinicalTrials.gov	Feb 2029	pending

The first set of results of Study A that have already been posted is the ThrombUS+ Training and Testing Data Set #1, which contains 2 separate data sets: a training data set and a testing data set. The training dataset includes 2341 anonymized compression ultrasound videos from 4 anatomical sites on the leg, acquired from

¹ Kaggle (<https://www.kaggle.com>) is the world's leading online platform and community for data science and machine learning. It was founded in 2010 and is now a subsidiary of Google. It features more than 500,000 data sets submitted by the public and has held more than 10,000 competitions. There are more than 27 million user accounts.

594 patients in 5 different hospitals. The dataset also includes anonymized metadata with patient demographics, biometrics and ground truth based on video assessment by expert radiologists. The accompanying testing dataset includes 578 compression ultrasound videos from the same 4 anatomical sites, acquired from another 148 patients, accompanied by metadata which however have the ground truth masked to the public at this point. The details of the data set are presented in the Annex.

Posting of a second Study A dataset is planned for June 2026, again including a training dataset with all available metadata and a testing dataset with the ground truth masked.

A final posting of Study A dataset is planned for February 2027, again including a training dataset with all available metadata and a testing dataset with the ground truth masked.

The unmasked ground truth for the testing sub-set is planned either by the end of the project or at 1-2 years later, depending on the requirements of data challenges planned by the consortium.

2. Study A Progress and Plan for Completion

Study A experienced initial delays in recruitment mainly due to:

- Delays in getting the ethics approvals. This was primarily because the main project documents needed to be translated into the local languages of the participating countries (this is only needed once, for the 1st study, and will be used again for subsequent submissions for the rest of the project studies. There have also been some additional delays with HSV, the French participating site. This is because the process coincided with the 2024 Paris Olympics, where HSV was acting as a supporting medical centre.
- Recruitment rates were lower than expected due to patient availability and willingness to participate.

One of the originally planned clinical sites, Partner TAU, was unable to participate in Study A after all. Proposed measures to address reduced rates in recruitment were discussed in the Consortium during spring 2025 and include:

- motivational emails and regular communication with site teams, to encourage recruitment and address challenges in real time, e.g., communicating non-invasive nature, contribution to medical innovation, and potential future patient benefits, etc.
- direct discussions during Monitoring Visits and the Project Consortium Meeting, which have helped realign expectations and clarify and refine already established operational workflows,
- ongoing performance monitoring, including tracking of enrolment trends and site-specific feedback loops, and monthly calls to address site-specific barriers quickly,
- using hospital websites or social media to inform patients about the study as well as
- addition of a new clinical site, namely the University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli (PGNA), Greece.

These measures were applied, and the recruitment rate shows a satisfactory increase during the last few months, as can be deduced from the recruitment rate per calendar month all 5 clinical sites as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Patient enrolment progress during the first 12 months for Study A deployment across all five clinical sites: number of enrolled patients per month (blue) and number of DVT cases (orange).

The current total number of recruited patients is 1092. As of now, recruitment continues at a steady pace.

Based on the recruitment rate of the past few months, we can safely assume an average recruitment rate of ~145 patients per month.

Then we can expect to reach the total number of 3000 patients by the end of 2026, based on the calculation: 145 patients X 14 months = 2030 patients additional to the current number of 1092 patients.

The updated plan to successfully conclude Study A by the end of 2026 includes:

- Continue current recruitment efforts without interruption.
- Sustain site motivation through personalized outreach and regular updates.
- Explore the possibility of reallocating recruitment focus to higher-performing sites.
- Dedicate online Investigator Meeting for discussing site’s capabilities and follow up strategies.

ANNEX: ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1

The first batch of Study A data, titled ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1, consists of anonymized compression ultrasound videos scanned at 4 different anatomical locations of the leg, acquired from left, right or both legs, depending on the clinical symptoms, accompanied by anonymized demographic and biometric information and expert's assessment of the compressibility and DVT.

The set includes 2 different subsets: a training data set of approximately 80% of the data and corresponding metadata including ground truth, and a testing data set of approximately 20% of the data and the corresponding metadata with the ground truth masked.

This first data set is intended to be used for the 1st ThrombUS+ data challenge to be organized within the BIOSTEC 2026: 19th International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies, Marbella, Spain, 2-4 March 2026 (<https://biostec.scitevents.org/>).

Data collection overview

For each patient, the first ultrasound compression video is acquired near the inguinal ligament, where the common femoral vein (CFV) and the common femoral artery (CFA) is visualized. The second compression video is recorded a few centimeters distally to the previous site, where the great saphenous vein (GSV) branches off of the common femoral vein (CFV). The third compression video is acquired in the middle of the thigh, where the femoral vein (FV) is visualized. Finally, compression of the popliteal vein (PV), behind the knee, is recorded.

In addition to the compression ultrasound videos, other eCRF-related data, including sex, age, height, weight, body mass index, thigh circumference, and a structured report, were recorded per patient. The structured report is based on the compression ultrasound video interpretation and diagnosis made by medical experts.

For each available anatomical site, medical experts report the compressibility (as no, partial, or yes) and the diagnosis of thrombosis (as no or yes). Thereby this information can be used as the ground truth annotations made by medical experts and subsequently employed for training and validating machine or deep learning models.

Data collection manual is available in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16913651>

Data collection is performed in 5 different clinical sites in 4 countries, based on explicit informed consent and after ethics approvals by respective independent committees as shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. The four anatomical sites of the right leg where ultrasound compression videos were recorded from. Ultrasound probe (red rectangle) was positioned perpendicular to the respective veins and used for compression. CFV: common femoral vein, GSV: great saphenous vein, FV: femoral vein, Pop: popliteal vein.

Table 1. Data collection clinical sites and respective ethics approvals

Hospital	Ethics Committee	Ethics Approval
LT1 LMSU Lithuanian University of Health Science Kaunas, Lithuania	Kaunas Regional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee, Kaunas, Lithuania	BE-2-107/05.11.2024 Approved on 05.11.2024
GA1 GNP Papageorgiou General Hospital Thessaloniki, Greece	Ethics Committee, Scientific Council of General Hospital of Thessaloniki "Papageorgiou", Thessaloniki, Greece	2024-B2015-376 Approved on 21.08.2024
IT1 CSS-IRCCS Home Relief of Suffering Hospital Foggia, Italy	Comitato Etico Fondazione Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza, Foggia, Italy	165/CE/2024 Approved on 12.11.2024
FR1 HSV Simon Veil Hospital Montmorency, France	Comité de Protection des Personnes Est III, CHRU de Nancy - Bâtiment principal - Rez de chaussée, Vandoeuvre-Les-Nancy, France	CPP 24.11.06 Approved on 05.11.2024
GR2 PGNA University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli Alexandroupoli, Greece	Ethics Committee, Scientific Council of University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli, Greece	ΕΣ1/09-01-2025 Approved on 09.01.2025

Data set #1 overview

The dataset is composed of a total 2919 DICOM compression ultrasound videos, each corresponding to 100-150 frames. The videos were acquired from 742 enrolled patients recruited in 5 European hospitals, two from Greece (GR1, GR2), one from Lithuania (LT1), one from Italy (IT1) and one from France (FR1).

The distribution of enrolled patients per hospital and the distribution of recorded videos per hospital are shown in Figure 3A and Figure 3B, respectively. The dataset includes videos from 408 females (55.0%) and from 334 males (45.0%) (Figure 3C). Out of the 106 DVT positive patients, 53 are females (50.0%) and 53 are male (50.0%) (Figure 3D). Regarding patient demographics and body-based metrics, the mean age of patients enrolled in the study is 65.01 ± 15.24 years, with a mean height of 167.79 ± 9.82 cm and a mean weight of 80.53 ± 19.20 kg (values in mean \pm SD, from $n=742$ patients) (Figure 3E).

Out of the 2919 available videos in the dataset, 734 (25.1%) present compressions on the common femoral vein (CFV), 726 (24.9%) on the great saphenous vein (GSV), 733 (25.1%) on the femoral vein and 726 (24.9%) on the popliteal veins (Figure 4A). Similarly, when comparing laterality, we found that the proposals are very close, with 1480 (50.7%) correspond to left limb and 1439 (49.3%) to the right limb (Figure 4B). These metrics indicate a nearly balanced dataset with respect to the anatomical sites.

Out of the 2919 videos, only 204 (7.0%) correspond to deep vein thrombosis (DVT) positive scans with the remaining 2715 (93.0%) present fully compressible veins, indicating the absence of thrombosis at the respective anatomical site (Figure 4D). Furthermore, the prevalence of positive to thrombosis scans varies across anatomical sites. In most cases, deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is present in the left popliteal vein (L-PV; 19.1%). The left common femoral vein (L-CFV) and the left femoral vein (L-FV) follow, each with a percentage of 17.2%. Thrombosis in the right popliteal vein (R-PV) is the third most frequent, representing 14.7% of the positive cases. Subsequently, thrombosis in the left great saphenous (L-GS; 9.8%), in the right femoral vein

(R-FV; 7.8%), in the right common femoral vein (R-CFV; 7.4%) and lastly in the right great saphenous (R-GS; 6.9%) are observed (Figure 4D).

All videos are provided in DICOM format, while metadata are provided as UTF-8 encoded CSV files.

Figure 3. ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1: (A) Number of enrolled patients per hospital; (B) Number of available video recordings per hospital; (C) number of patients per sex; (D) number of DVT positive patients per sex. (E) The age (65.01 ± 15.24 ; mean \pm SD), height (167.79 ± 9.82 cm; mean \pm SD) and weight (80.53 ± 19.20 kg; mean \pm SD) distributions of enrolled patients ($n=742$).

Figure 4. ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1: (A) Video distribution per anatomical site. (B) Video distribution per limb. (C) Video distribution per DVT or Not-DVT. (D) DVT positive video distribution per anatomical site.

Overview of the Training and Testing Subsets

The dataset was stratified into training and testing subsets to ensure as much as possible proportional representation of DVT and non-DVT videos, participants' sex, major demographics, biometrics parameters, anatomical sites, left and right scans, and clinical sites across both subsets (Figure 5).

In particular, the training subset consists of 2341 videos acquired from 594 patients, while the testing subset consists of 578 videos acquired from 148 patients. Figure 5A and Figure 5B presents the patient demographics and biometrics distributions for training and testing subset respectively. Figure 6A and Figure 6B present patient provenance of training and testing subset respectively with respect to the 5 contributing clinical sites, while Figure 6C and Figure 6D present video provenance for training and testing subset respectively with

respect to the 5 contributing clinical sites. Figure 6E and Figure 6F present the distribution of videos per left or right leg in the training and testing subsets respectively

Although data stratification was performed so as to ensure as much as possible similar distributions of videos per anatomical site, right-left leg and DVT or non-DVT in the training and testing subsets, **the exact distributions are not disclosed at this time so as to maintain scientific rigor and prevent data dredging in the challenge that is organized based on these data. The full detailed description of the stratification into training and testing data subsets will be disclosed after the completion of the respective data challenge, in the data description in Zenodo.**

Figure 5. Overview of ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1 as split in Training and Testing subsets. Left column presents the demographics and biometrics distribution of the patients contributing data for the training subset while the right column the respective distributions for the testing subset.

Figure 6. Overview of ThrombUS+ Study A Data Set #1 as split in Training and Testing subsets. (A) and (B) present patient provenance in the training and testing subsets respectively; (C) and (D) present video provenance in the training and testing subsets respectively; and (E) and (F) present the distribution of videos per left or right leg in the training and testing subsets respectively.

Download ThrombUS+ Data Set #1:

Training subset #1: <https://zenodo.org/records/17659415>

Testing subset #1: <https://zenodo.org/records/17664207>